

Balancing the Trade-off between Data Center Development and Its Environmental Impacts: A Comparative Analysis of Policymaking in Singapore and Amsterdam

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Abstract

Data centers are the backbone of digitalization, deemed a necessary infrastructure to enable digital services. This strategic role turned data center deployment into a policymaking priority for places receptive to digitalization. However, recent policies marked a sharp rupture of the prevailing policy paradigm in two data center hubs, Singapore and Amsterdam. The 2019 data center moratoriums in Amsterdam and Singapore temporarily halted the construction of data centers, breaking with the historical fostering of digital infrastructure growth that both places incentivized. This work investigates the motivation for the data policy change. We study to what extent the policy decisions on moratorium were influenced by consideration of the tradeoff between data center development and its environmental impacts. Our findings suggest that Singapore declared the moratorium because of environmental impacts and adopted a more balanced approach between digitalization and sustainability. Yet, the same two elements are not observed to the same degree for Amsterdam, where the moratorium decision was motivated by problems in urban planning and the energy infrastructure. Beyond the particularities of the cases, studying moratoriums can provide insight into the options available to policymakers in the face of rapid digital infrastructure growth. In the short-term, moratoriums can buy additional time for policy re-evaluation, and, in contrast to more passive approaches, temporarily avoid further environmental impacts of data center growth. However, the long-term effects of moratoriums on the sustainability of digital infrastructure are uncertain. These effects will depend, among other factors, on policymakers' ability to comprehensively evaluate data center policies and build on short-term course corrections to achieve lasting policy transformation.

Keywords: *data center; policy change; digital infrastructure; environmental impact*